

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A576

16 September 1997

ACSOE

Flight Investigating Outflow
from Hurricane Erica

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 576

DATE: 16/9/197

Take off: 1215

Landing: 1430

Aircraft Scientist : A. KATE
Flight Leader : I. PORE
Others CO : S. SCHMITZEN
MRY : S. BAUWITTE
ECAL : J. KENT
PSTLAS : D. ARTHUR
CNZ, PSAP EIC : K. DEWEY
FORWARD SIDE : G. MILLS
PERORIDE : B. BANDY
PERCA : T. GREEN

Captain : D. BONDALL
Co-pilot : C. O'BRIEN
Navigator : T. SIMPSON
Engineer : K. QUICK
Loadmaster : M. LEMMAUS

+ P. MONKS
S. PERKETT
K. LOW
C. REEVES } MISSION SCIENTISTS

Trials Instructions : MRF 1 : ACROE
Operating area : N. ATLANTIC W/ AZORES

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A576, 16th September, 1997
 ACSOE
 North Atlantic near the Azores

Start time	End time	Event	Height(s)	Hdg	Comments
121650					Take off St Maria
122826	124329	R1	FL80	220°	
125031	132835	P1	50' FL200	230°	Bottles filled at 1000', 5000', FL100, FL150, FL200
133010	135233	P2	FL200 50'	220°	
135233	142804	P3	50' FL200	220°	Bottles filled @ FL50, FL100 FL150, FL200
142925	145759	P4	FL200 50'	210°	Bottles filled @ FL190
145759	153124	P5	50' FL200	210°	Bottles filled @ 1000', FL170, FL200
153518	160821	P6	FL200 50'	210°	Bottles filled @ FL150, FL100, FL60, 3000', 1000', 500'
160821	170217	P7	50' FL200	030°	Bottles filled @ 100', 1500', 4000', FL80, FL120, FL170, FL190
161202	161629	R2	100'	025°	
170217	171814	P8	FL200 FL50	025°	
171814	172827	P9	FL50 FL150	020°	
173141	174211	P10	F150 FL50	020°	
174211	175252	P11	FL50 FL150	020°	
175252	180440	P12	FL150 FL50	015°	
180727	181807	P13	FL50 FL150	015°	
181807	182818	P14	FL150 FL50	015°	
183040	184102	P15	FL50 FL150	020°	
193319					Land St Maria

A576

GPS data
08:08:13 - 19:40:30

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A576 Date: 16/9/97 User: H. VICTOR
Interactive by: I. RICE/D. TODD/AN
Date: 29/9/97

Renav HUMAN FILTERING USED

TWC

Profile plotted : NO
Line chosen : Profile Whole flight / Other

a = - 0.5879E+1
b = + 0.2482E-2
c = + 0.367E-6

LWC

Heimann / Barnes

NOT USED

A576 ACSOE SCIENCE

September 16, 1997

Aircraft Scientist Debrief:

Weather:

The weather was dominated by Tropical Storm Erica which passed to the north of the Azores during the night. As we proceeded to the south there was a clear transition into an airmass which was less cloudy, more hazy with a calmer sea.

Instrumentation:

Takeoff was delayed due to serious problems with the NO_x instrument. The high humidity during the night had caused excessive condensation around the dry-ice cooled detectors. The resultant flood was mopped up and the instrument dried out (with the help of a hairdrier from the hotel!) before the electrical power could be connected. Once airborne, there were no significant problems with the instrumentation.

Overview:

This was a successful sortie. The mission scientists were very pleased with the data collected during the flight. We did full depth sawtooths from Santa Maria out and high level sawtooths on the return track after a full depth stepped profile into and out of the most southerly point. The contrast between the two airmasses was clear, and the transition was clearly visible during the sawtoothing out and back.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: AC80E
Flight No: A576

Date: 16/09/97
Page 1 of 5

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:24:19	3000 ft climb @ 3200	Pres Rad FL			level moved slightly up to clear a thin layer of Sc clouds.
12:28:25	R1	080 Pres Rad FL	222	36.50 -25.56	< 1/8 broken cu below, clear above. large cu ahead and on either side.
12:33:40	R1	080 Pres Rad FL	219	36.16 -25.83	strata of very fine cu below, Sc ahead, some active cu: one ahead with a small cumil.
12:41:42	R1	Pres Rad FL			passing over a small linear small cu feature.
12:43:28	R1 end	080 Pres Rad FL	226	35.57 -26.44	Sc ahead with some active ahead. cloud top - cloud bottom -
12:50:28	P1 start	50 Pres Rad FL	219	35. -26.	DEISSE ON WINDOWS. Very heavy 6/8 sc above, some gaps visible in cloud. 1016 sea state 4
		1000 Pres Rad FL			profile interrupted for NOxy and CO. zeros at 1000ft.
		080 Pres Rad FL			12:56:40 - some drizzle 12:57:51 - end of drizzle - 3300ft.
13:00:34		050 Pres Rad FL	281	34.95 -27.27	NOxy zero, turned the a/c westward to miss bank of Cu.
		Pres Rad FL			Some very big cu on all sides. -
13:07:12		100 Pres Rad FL	281	34.83 -27.55	8/8 sc below. many big cu, clear above.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Karge

Project: ACS06

Flight No: A57C

Date: 16/09/97

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:17:09	P1	150 Pres Rad FL	182	34.18 -27.50	4/8 sc below some low cir - clear above.
13:28:39	P1 end	200 Pres Rad FL	184	34.40 -27.49	Small cir fields below. clear above some sc ahead.
13:30:10	P2	200 Pres Rad FL	185	33.28 -27.50	.
13:36:29		130 Pres Rad FL	183	32.87 -27.50	Clear below and sc ahead. 13:39:42 resume profile.
13:52:33	P2 & P3s.	50 Pres Rad FL	206	31.89 -27.41	Very Hazy ... broken small cir below. clear above.
14:01:09		50 Pres Rad FL	202	31.54 -27.55	Passing just ahead to a large cir to starboard. (13:59:06) some alto cir ahead. Some small cir fields below
14:08:25		100 Pres Rad FL	202	31.16 -27.69	Resume climb @ 14:02:19. Small cir fields below! Some thin ci above to port clear above S3D.
14:10:59		150 Pres Rad FL	202	30.66 -27.84	Very Dry layer @ 12400 14:14:20. 7/8 ci above not very transparent. 45° below visible 14:19:26 Cs cirro stratus.
14:24:02		Pres Rad FL		30.29 -27.96	apparent change in clouds below. Small cir ending and giving way to CS above and hazy below. CS thickening to edge
14:28:21	P2 P4s	200 Pres Rad FL	187	30.02 -28.02	Hazy below Cs ahead. @ no cloud below but occasional small cir fields are visible.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye .

Project: ACS06
Flight No: A576

Date: 16 / 09 / 97
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:41:06	P4 Cont.	090 Pres Rad FL	185	29.43 -28.00	Broken high level CS ahead, some small layers small ci below hazy layer below
14:58:00	P4e P53	50' Pres Rad FL	184	29.30 -28.74	7/8 ci above small cir. and hazy calm sea
		Pres Rad FL			1000 ft 15:00:08 altimeters zeroed. resume @ 15:02:50
		Pres Rad FL			Very hazy layer after inversion. CNC shows no structure, Ken going to investigate...
15:15:00		095 Pres Rad FL	197	27.38 -28.47	hazy layer below with some very small cir. below. 5/8 ci above, clear ahead.
15:23:02		170 Pres Rad FL	193	26.84 -28.64	layer just abv. F.105, 700mb Res hazy below, ci above and very small cir. at surface. Resume @ 15:26:44
15:31:24		200 Pres Rad FL	194	26.33 -28.75	Same.
15:35:18	P6 ↓	200 Pres Rad FL	195	26.05 -28.81	clear & hazy below (ie. now cloud) northern edge of ci above. Hazy ahead
15:48:12	RC ↓	100 Pres Rad FL	191	25.23 -28.90	FL150 15:40:50 Restart @ 15:42:40 FL100 - < 1/8 small cir below Resume @ 15:49:08
15:53:22		060 Pres Rad FL	189	24.92 -29.06	< 1/8 thin cir below. Hazy ahead clear above. Restarting 15:56:29

No. 11 min cal @ level of

1020 wastek 4

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kays*

Project: ACSOE
Flight No: A576

Date: 16/5/97
Page 4 of 5

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:57:42	P6 ↓	3000 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	194	24.57 -29.15	3/8 cu below hazy ahead. clear above wind swinging around Restart 16:00:17 8 minutes ago.
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			1000 ft — 16:03:58 — 16:04:28 { cloud layer between 2000ft 500 ft. — 16:05:41 — 16:07:18 } and 1500.
16:08:10	P ↓	50 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	194	24.15 -29.29	clear and clear with ~ 2/8 cu above — 1420 sea state 3
16:12:02	P7 ↑	100 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	9	24.14 -29.29	aircraft turned around 16:12:02. Resume @ 16:16:29, and pointed for home. 2000 ft. 16:20:21 Restart.
16:51:00	P ↑	170 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	12	26.21 -28.75	small cu fields below, ci above.
16:55:17	P7 ↑	190 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	6	26.48 -28.69	less small cu below, more ci above — instrument zeros. Restart 17:01:16
17:02:17	P7 → P8 ↓	200 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	10	27.00 -28.57	clear above, use traces of cu near surface.
17:16:14	P8 ↓ P9 ↑	50 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	12	28.27 -28.30	hazy below. old cloud contrail → visible in shadow 20:10 on surface, looks like a tadpole.
17:29:29	P9 ↑ P10 ↓	150 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	9	28.96 -29.12	more active cu ahead and some sheets of sc.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: *AESOE*
Flight No: *A576*

Date: *16/9/97*
Page *5* of *5*

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude ----- Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
<i>17:31:48</i>	<i>P10 u start</i>	<i>150</i> 200	<i>11</i>	<i>34.11</i> <i>-28.09</i>	<i>large layer @ about <u>FL95</u></i>
<i>17:42:11</i>	<i>P10 we P11 9s</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>30.07</i> <i>-27.87</i>	<i>Small cu fields about same active cu. 1/8 ci above.</i>
<i>18:04:46</i>	<i>P12 u P13 7</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>359</i>	<i>31.72</i> <i>-27.53</i>	<i>Towering cu all around us. Rainbows visible under clouds under one cu with a lenticular cloud on top. start of P13: start 18:07:27</i>
<i>18:18:07</i>	<i>P13 7e P14 4s</i>	<i>150</i>		<i>32.83</i> <i>-27.42</i>	<i>clouds have now changed, many more cu, with intermixed SC sheets.</i>
<i>18:28:17</i>	<i>P14 e P15 7</i>	<i>50</i>		<i>33.68</i> <i>-27.30</i>	<i>4/8 cu below, clear above, P15 start 18:30:40</i>
<i>18:40:02</i>	<i>P15 end</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>34.59</i> <i>-27.09</i>	<i>Broken cu and sc below. clear above</i>
					<i>instrument serv's</i>
<i>18:45:10</i>		<i>150</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>34.91</i> <i>-26.99</i>	<i>END OF FORMAL SCIENCE — INSTRUMENT OPERATORS WILL DO CALS AND NO. IN ARTIFACT</i>

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 16/a/a7

Date: 16/a/a7

A/S Name: A. KATE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for SEVERAL FOR NAME
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period INDEF
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project AESOE
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? INDEF
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A576 Date: 16/9/97

Page...!...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	<u>0567</u>	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	<u>2854</u>	✓			Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	<u>4045</u>	<u>F/S</u> O/S	TORQUE <u>4.0</u>		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	<u>4015</u>	<u>F/S</u> O/S	TORQUE <u>3.0</u>		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	<u>2200</u>	✓			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	<u>3861</u>	<u>950</u>	✓		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	<u>3290</u>	<u>1000</u>			
	A/S	9	<u>0087</u>	✓			As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	<u>0401</u>		<u>JOLD</u>		
	UP2S	82	<u>0633</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>RED</u>		
	UIRS	83	<u>0282</u>		<u>JNDZ</u>		
	UP1Z	84	<u>0376</u>				Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	<u>0144</u>	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	<u>0270</u>				Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	<u>0682</u>				As IAT
	UP2T	88	<u>2371</u>	<u>+23</u>			As IAT
	UIRT	89	<u>0000</u>				As IAT
	LP1S	91	<u>0055</u>		<u>JOLD</u>		
	LP2S	92	<u>0144</u>	<u>-10</u>	<u>RED</u>		
	LIRS	93	<u>0013</u>		<u>JNDZ</u>		
	LP1Z	94	<u>0055</u>				Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	<u>249</u>	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	<u>0013</u>				Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	<u>0220</u>				As IAT
	LP2T	98	<u>2362</u>	<u>+23</u>			As IAT
	LIRT	99	<u>0000</u>				As IAT
	J/W	42	<u>0996</u>	<u>0.0</u>	✓		As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	<u>745</u>				
	HYGR	58	<u>3474</u>				
	HYCC	59	<u>0706</u>	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	<u>0197</u>		<u>CAL</u>		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	<u>0008</u>				
	DTF	10	<u>1038</u>	<u>23</u>			
	DTC	11	<u>0</u>				
	NDTF	23	<u>1787</u>	<u>23</u>			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	<u>0</u>				
	INCT	48	<u>2710</u>				
	CCN	140	<u>4</u>				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	<u>4005</u>	✓			0000-4094 <u>4095</u>
	TSAM	72	<u>0216</u>	✓			0640-1860 <u>< min</u>
	O3	100	<u>0002</u>				
	O3P	106	<u>226</u>				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	<u>1780</u>				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	576			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0025			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0436			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	9			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3766	3856 1684	3766	0481	3766	3657	3762	0940
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 0

GMT	PARA.	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	4025	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1271	✓		2000-3460 < min	
	TSAM	72	046	✓		0640-1860 < min	
	TAMB	73	2586	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	258	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1084	✓		0000-4095 < 4095	
	HTR2	76	2127	✓		0000-4095 < 4095	
	ISRC	77	1027			0001-1230 < min	
	STAT	78	1688			4095	
	EV1V	170	2023				
	EV2V	171	2023				
	NPWR	172	3327				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear J01D	Off/ On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red R01		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon J02		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear J01D	Off/ On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon J02		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A576 Date: 16/9/97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2854				Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	1895	✓ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1934	✓ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	1695	7500			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2208	8000	FUSO		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	2648	740	✓		
	A/S	9	2644	757	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	4095		JOID		
	UP2S	82	2075		RED		
	UIRS	83	0560		JNO		
	UP1Z	84	4095		JOID		Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0142	✓	RED		Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	0564		JNO		Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	4095		JOID		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2447		RED		As IAT
	UIRT	89	0000		JNA		As IAT
	LP1S	91	1937				
	LP2S	92	0162		✓		
	LIRS	93	0235				
	LP1Z	94	1940				Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0147	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	0236				Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	0247				As IAT
	LP2T	98	2437				As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000				As IAT
	J/W	42	1472	0.2			As Indicated 0000
	HYGR	58	2945	15			
	HYCC	59	0715				696-901
	FDEW	138	2180				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	0108				
	DTF	10	2741	26			
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	2735	26			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	6				
	INCT	48	2638				
	HEIM	141	2963				
	PRTC	142	2383	✓			approx 2380
	TWCD	70	2020	✓			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	1287	✓			0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	0082				
	O3P	106	1045				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	277				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	576			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0731			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0450			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	21			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3122	1284 3857	7123	0730	3102	3711	3111	0776
	LATC	160	Dec	0340	34		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3783	27		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: ↗

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	1460	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2577	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1028	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2737	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2234	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1122	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1233	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1023	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	11045	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3491				
	EV2V	171	3142				
	NPWR	172	2625				
	EVIC	173	3228				
	EV2C	174	3928				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 576.....

Date 16/9/97.....

Page 1..... of 2.....

Video Tape	
No.	A576#1
Ends	1531
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36° 58.36N	36° 57.36N
Long	025° 09.46W	25° 09.47
Time	0924	0925
Status	Ss	RC ALGN

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
080725				DATA ON					
115430				SET INU TO NAV					
121650				T/O SANDA MANA					
				START RWY 1					
122526	10	FL80		220	230	11.7	1.0		
123109	11		START VIDEO						COUNT = 0000
124131	12			SWITCH TO DFC					
124329	13	FL80		240	END RWY 1				
124448	14			SWITCH TO FFC					
125031	15	50'	106	230	START P1 ↗				SS = 4
125220	16	1000'		235	INTERUPT P1				
125418	17	1000'		250	RESTART P1				
130034	18	8000'		245	INTERUPT P1				
130200	19	5000'		240	RESTART P1				
130715	20	FL400		190	INTERUPT P1				
130737	21	FL400		195	RESTART P1				
131704	22	FL450		195	INTERUPT P1				
131851	23	FL150		195	RESTART P1				
132836	24	FL200		195	END P1			NOXY ZERO	
133010	25	FL200		200	START P2 ↓				
133629	26	FL130		195	INTERUPT P2				
133945	27	FL130			RESTART P2				
135232	28	50'	106	220	END P2 / START P3				SS = 4/5
140107	29	FL130		215	INTERUPT P3				

Video Tape	
No.	A576 #1
Ends	1531
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	30 09.60N	30 07.31N
Long	28 00.56W	28 00.15W
Time	1426	1426
Status	Ss	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
140319	30	FL50		215	RESTART		P3		
140824	31	FL100		220	INTERRUPT		P3		
14113	32	FL100		215	RESTART		P3		
141756	33	FL50		215	INTERRUPT		P3		
141926	34	FL50		210	RESTART		P3		
142804	35	FL200		200	END		P3		
142925	36	FL200		200	START		P4		
144100	37	FL90		205	INTERRUPT		P4		
144448	38	FL90		205	RESTART		P4		
146759	39	50'	1020	210	END P4 / START		P5		SS=4
150008	40	1000'		210	INTERRUPT		P5		
150150	42	1000'		210	RESTART		P5		
152344	44	FL170		210	INTERRUPT		P5		
152644	45	FL170		210	RESTART		P5		
153124	47	FL200		210	END		P5		DATA FILE
153153	48		START VIDEO		A576 #1		COUNT = 6134		
153238	49		START VIDEO		A576 #2		COUNT = 1000		
153511	50	FL200		210	START		P6		
154050	51	FL50		210	INTERRUPT		P6		
154240	52	FL50		210	RESTART		P6		
154813	53	FL100		210	INTERRUPT		P6		
154908	54	FL100		210	RESTART		P6		
155320	55	FL100		210	INTERRUPT		P6		
156029	56	FL100		205	RESTART		P6		
155944	57	FL100		210	INTERRUPT		P6		
160015	58	3000'		210	RESTART		P6		
160356	59	1000'		210	INTERRUPT		P6		
160428	60	1000'		210	RESTART		P6		
160542	62	500'		210	INTERRUPT		P6		
160715	63	500'		210	RESTART		P6		
160921	64	50'		210	END P6 / START		P7		SS=3
161022	65	100'	1020	210	INTERRUPT		P7 / START		RUN 2
161202	67				INTERRUPT				

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No **A 576** Date **16/9/97** Page **2** of **2**

Video Tape	
No.	A576#2
Ends	1832
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	25 26.05N	25 27.29N
Long	28 56.80W	28 56.30W
Time	1638	1639
Status	Ss	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
161620	68	100'		025					
161822	69	2000'		030					
162155		1500							
162403	70	1500		030					
163031	71	4000'		030					
163922	72	4000		030					080
164015	74	FL080		030					
164377	75	FL080		030					
164409	76	FL120		030					
164658	77	FL120		030					
165051	78	FL170		030					
165251		FL170		030					
165516	80	FL190		030					
170116	81	FL190		030					
170417	82	FL200		025					
171814	83	FL050		025					
172827	84	FL150		020					
173114	85	FL150		020					
174211	86	FL150		020					
175252	87	FL150		020					
180440	88	FL150							
180727	89	FL150		015					
181107	90	FL150		015					
182118	91	FL150		015					
183040	92	FL150		020					
183107	93	END TAPE							
183205	94	START TAPE							
184102	95	FL150							

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

 Flight No. **A 576**

 Date **16/9/97**

 Sheet no. **1**

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
1	P3 B6			FL 200	153000 153125	153125	153505	465	purge at run start fill at run start P6 5.5 bar. 200
2	P3 P7			FL 150	153600	154052	155235	574	fill at run start 6.4 bar 150
3	P3 B11			FL 100	154530	154816	154905	699	fill at run start 100
4	P3 B12			FL 060	155016	155550	155625	816	purge fill and of zeros on run * 060
5	P3 B2			3000'	155800	155944	160012		3000' 3000'
6	Z1			1000'	160130	160400	160426	987	1000
7	P3 B5			500'	160520	160648	160711	1006	flush extend into run 1 run. 500
8	Z02			100'	160830	161503	161528	1018	extended flush P7 * 100
9	B9			2000'	161600	162025	162053		(some cloud) 2000' 2000'
10	R42			1500'	162320	162530	162558	969	extra. 1500'
11	R20			4000'	162700	163040	163118	881	4000
12	H4			4000' 080	163214	163615	163658	753	080
13	Z05			120	163800	164421	164528	646	* 120

PAN GC Log

①

GC Sample record			Flight Number: D576					Operator: Joss					Date: 16/9/97			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = 14					Optimisation = 11				Optimisation = 13.				
			Back Flush = 37.					Back Flush = 42.5.				Back Flush = 37.6.				
			Flow rate = 36					Flow rate = 36.1				Flow rate = 36.6				
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP				
#1	114658	Ground														
#2	115414	Ground	446	1557			477	1861			249	1784				
#3	122915	FLO80	453	1261			483	1527			456	1418			Peak 1. P.	
#4	123434	FLO80	455	1268			484	1526			457	1427			Peak 1. P.	
#5	130748	1000	455	1535			477	1832			458	1750			Peak 2. P.	
#6	130748	A100	455	1253			487	1527			458	1439			P.	
#7	131754	FL150	457	1167			489	1445			459	1363			Peak 1	
#8	140838	FL600	451	1246			487	1502			456	1426			P2.	
#9	141416	FL130	451	1175			486	1365			455	1353			P2	
#10	142646	FL200	451	1079			486	1271			454	1235			P2 top.	
#11	144050	FL090	450	1275			484	1527			451	1466			P4.	
#12	150004	1000'	443	1545			479	1956			446	1770			PS.	
#13	FL140	152028	441	1165			478	1441			446	1358				

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <u>AS76</u>					Operator: <u>Joss</u>					Date: <u>18/9/97</u>			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = <u>14</u>					Optimisation = <u>4</u>				Optimisation = <u>13</u>				
			Back Flush = <u>37</u>					Back Flush = <u>42.5</u>				Back Flush = <u>37.6</u>				
			Flow rate = <u>36</u>					Flow rate = <u>36.1</u>				Flow rate = <u>36.6</u>				
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
#14	<u>152547</u>	<u>FL170</u>	<u>442</u>	<u>1100</u>				<u>478</u>	<u>1335</u>			<u>447</u>	<u>1281</u>			
#15	<u>153116</u>	<u>FL200</u>	<u>442</u>	<u>1024</u>				<u>479</u>	<u>1206</u>			<u>448</u>	<u>1186</u>			
#16	<u>15404</u>	<u>FL50</u>	<u>443</u>	<u>1139</u>				<u>479</u>	<u>1341</u>			<u>448</u>	<u>1323</u>			<u>P.</u>
#17	<u>154815</u>	<u>FL100</u>	<u>443</u>	<u>1260</u>				<u>479</u>	<u>1496</u>			<u>448</u>	<u>1457</u>			
#18	<u>155348</u>	<u>FL200</u>	<u>443</u>	<u>1384</u>				<u>479</u>	<u>1651</u>			<u>448</u>	<u>1596</u>			
#19	<u>160007</u>	<u>BCO0'</u>	<u>443</u>	<u>1486</u>				<u>479</u>	<u>1783</u>			<u>448</u>	<u>1716</u>			
#20	<u>160535</u>	<u>500'</u>	<u>442</u>	<u>1578</u>				<u>479</u>	<u>1909</u>			<u>448</u>	<u>1816</u>			
#21	<u>161252</u>	<u>FL120</u>	<u>460</u>	<u>1151</u>				<u>493</u>	<u>1502</u>			<u>466</u>	<u>1411</u>			

DATE 16 9 97		MRF TI	01	NAVIGATOR				Flt Lt 'SIMMO' Simpson			
AIRFIELD		TEMPERATURE ST WADY						VOR 1 SMA TAC 1 NL			
ATIS		R/W	18	°C +23/21		QNH	1012	2988	VOR 2 TAC 2 ✓		
1150 z		W/V	270	08			QFE	ADFSMA 323			
		Wx					RPS	Rte Salt 3100			
		Cloud					LFP	1012	MSFL 3500'		
ATC: FP		220				SSR: 2000		INS NAV 2 1154			
A/B 1217		S/H	1218	F/T	8.00						
				ETA	2018						
Time	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT	QNH	LAT/LONG		RUN
122825	230	6P	200	180	220	270 31	FL80	1013	N 36299 W 02534.0		R1
124325	237	4P	283	180	294	280 25	✓	-	35354 02625.6		E✓
125030	228	1P	176	✓	190	270 15	50'	1016	35142 02647.7		P1
125220							1000	-	3510.0 02651.4		INS
125415							✓	-	35055 02656.6		P1
130035	290	15	180	-	202	280 18	5000	-	34565 02716.0		INT
130206	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	34576 027215		P1
130715							100	1013			INT
131036	190	4P	219	180	215	280 22	✓	-	34356 02732.3		P1
131705	195	-	230	-	230	285 21	150	-	3411.5 02730.6		INT
131850	-								34043 02738.4		P1
132836	197	3P	259	-	250	315 20	200	-	33245 02736.0		EP1
133010	-						4130	-	33177 02730.3		P2
133630	191	-	228	-	228	270 17	130	-	32504 02730.2		INT
133945							50'	-	32389 02729.8		P2
135253	222	4P	176	-	185	270 15	50'	1018	31572 02722.6		EP2/P
140107	213	6P	193	-	200	265 29	FL50	1013	31331 02734.2		INT
140319							✓		31263 02736.6		P3
140824	-					245 33	FL100	-	3110.6 02741.0		INT
141113	-						✓		31018 02743.9		P3
141756	216	4P	222	175	234	275 19	150		3039.5 02750.9		INT
141926							200		30240 02752.8		
142804	200	0	251	-	250	295 10	FL200	-	3000.7 02801.8		EP3
142925	-								-		P4
144100	203	2P	209	180	215	260 18	FL90	✓	2909.8 2804.9		INT
145800	208	2P					50'	1020	2815.2 02814.6		EP4
150250	-	-	182	-	187	260 13	✓	-	2800.9 02818.2		P5
152345	205	3P	222	-	240	295 13	170		2651.1 02836.3		INT
153124	-	4P	235	-	252	280 18	FL200	1013	2620.9 02844.5		EP5
153518	-	-	252				300 50'		2621.7 02847.9		P6
154813	205	2P	226	-	220	310 09	FL100	-	2515.7 02859.1		INT
154948							600	-	2510.3 02859.8		P6
155320	-	-	-	-	-	195 04	60	-	2456.0 02903.5		INT
ATIS	R/W	°C		QNH		LND					
z	W/V			QFE		A/B					
Wx							Time				
Cloud									CFWD		

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A576

DATE: 16/9/97

MRF 1

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	✓	✓	
HEIMANN	✓	✓	
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	✓	✓	
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	SOLD ✓	✓	
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	JN ₂ ✓	✓	
LOWER CLEAR	SOLD ✓	✓	
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	TN ₂ ✓	✓	
MARSS	X		
SAFIRE	X		
DEIMOS	X		
ARIES	X		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	X		
CLOUD PHYSICS	X		
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	X		
PSAP	✓	✓	

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

A576 16-SEP-97 Data starts 08:07:35 Data ends 19:37:09

Header file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A576_RAW_HDDR.DAT;
Data file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A576_RAW_DATA.DAT; 80.8 Mbytes (165480 blocks
)

Transcription on 25-SEP-97 09:12:02
Extraction on 25-SEP-97 09:12:02

Data set type 2

ISS 31 DBF 31 IC 02 121 parameters recorded 889 samples per second

3 sections of data

Section	Starts					Ends				
	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC
1	08:07:35	029255	000	00010	00001	14:19:55	051595	034	22350	22341
2	14:19:58	051598	034	22353	22342	14:57:55	053875	038	24630	24619
3	14:57:59	053879	039	24634	24620	19:37:09	070629	096	41384	41370

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log ✓ Chemistry log <i>BOTTLES, Etc</i> ✓
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log ✓ Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 28

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 16 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:200,000

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Gridinal scale 1:20m.

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX = 28

Prepared and drawn to the Cartographic Section, MET.O. (M) (C) (K) (R) (S) (T) (U) (V) (W) (X) (Y) (Z) (AA) (AB) (AC) (AD) (AE) (AF) (AG) (AH) (AI) (AJ) (AK) (AL) (AM) (AN) (AO) (AP) (AQ) (AR) (AS) (AT) (AU) (AV) (AW) (AX) (AY) (AZ) (BA) (BB) (BC) (BD) (BE) (BF) (BG) (BH) (BI) (BJ) (BK) (BL) (BM) (BN) (BO) (BP) (BQ) (BR) (BS) (BT) (BU) (BV) (BW) (BX) (BY) (BZ) (CA) (CB) (CC) (CD) (CE) (CF) (CG) (CH) (CI) (CJ) (CK) (CL) (CM) (CN) (CO) (CP) (CQ) (CR) (CS) (CT) (CU) (CV) (CW) (CX) (CY) (CZ) (DA) (DB) (DC) (DD) (DE) (DF) (DG) (DH) (DI) (DJ) (DK) (DL) (DM) (DN) (DO) (DP) (DQ) (DR) (DS) (DT) (DU) (DV) (DW) (DX) (DY) (DZ) (EA) (EB) (EC) (ED) (EE) (EF) (EG) (EH) (EI) (EJ) (EK) (EL) (EM) (EN) (EO) (EP) (EQ) (ER) (ES) (ET) (EU) (EV) (EW) (EX) (EY) (EZ) (FA) (FB) (FC) (FD) (FE) (FF) (FG) (FH) (FI) (FJ) (FK) (FL) (FM) (FN) (FO) (FP) (FQ) (FR) (FS) (FT) (FU) (FV) (FW) (FX) (FY) (FZ) (GA) (GB) (GC) (GD) (GE) (GF) (GG) (GH) (GI) (GJ) (GK) (GL) (GM) (GN) (GO) (GP) (GQ) (GR) (GS) (GT) (GU) (GV) (GW) (GX) (GY) (GZ) (HA) (HB) (HC) (HD) (HE) (HF) (HG) (HH) (HI) (HJ) (HK) (HL) (HM) (HN) (HO) (HP) (HQ) (HR) (HS) (HT) (HU) (HV) (HW) (HX) (HY) (HZ) (IA) (IB) (IC) (ID) (IE) (IF) (IG) (IH) (II) (IJ) (IK) (IL) (IM) (IN) (IO) (IP) (IQ) (IR) (IS) (IT) (IU) (IV) (IW) (IX) (IY) (IZ) (JA) (JB) (JC) (JD) (JE) (JF) (JG) (JH) (JI) (JJ) (JK) (JL) (JM) (JN) (JO) (JP) (JQ) (JR) (JS) (JT) (JU) (JV) (JW) (JX) (JY) (JZ) (KA) (KB) (KC) (KD) (KE) (KF) (KG) (KH) (KI) (KJ) (KK) (KL) (KM) (KN) (KO) (KP) (KQ) (KR) (KS) (KT) (KU) (KV) (KW) (KX) (KY) (KZ) (LA) (LB) (LC) (LD) (LE) (LF) (LG) (LH) (LI) (LJ) (LK) (LL) (LM) (LN) (LO) (LP) (LQ) (LR) (LS) (LT) (LU) (LV) (LW) (LX) (LY) (LZ) (MA) (MB) (MC) (MD) (ME) (MF) (MG) (MH) (MI) (MJ) (MK) (ML) (MM) (MN) (MO) (MP) (MQ) (MR) (MS) (MT) (MU) (MV) (MW) (MX) (MY) (MZ) (NA) (NB) (NC) (ND) (NE) (NF) (NG) (NH) (NI) (NJ) (NK) (NL) (NM) (NN) (NO) (NP) (NQ) (NR) (NS) (NT) (NU) (NV) (NW) (NX) (NY) (NZ) (OA) (OB) (OC) (OD) (OE) (OF) (OG) (OH) (OI) (OJ) (OK) (OL) (OM) (ON) (OO) (OP) (OQ) (OR) (OS) (OT) (OU) (OV) (OW) (OX) (OY) (OZ) (PA) (PB) (PC) (PD) (PE) (PF) (PG) (PH) (PI) (PJ) (PK) (PL) (PM) (PN) (PO) (PP) (PQ) (PR) (PS) (PT) (PU) (PV) (PW) (PX) (PY) (PZ) (QA) (QB) (QC) (QD) (QE) (QF) (QG) (QH) (QI) (QJ) (QK) (QL) (QM) (QN) (QO) (QP) (QQ) (QR) (QS) (QT) (QU) (QV) (QW) (QX) (QY) (QZ) (RA) (RB) (RC) (RD) (RE) (RF) (RG) (RH) (RI) (RJ) (RK) (RL) (RM) (RN) (RO) (RP) (RQ) (RR) (RS) (RT) (RU) (RV) (RW) (RX) (RY) (RZ) (SA) (SB) (SC) (SD) (SE) (SF) (SG) (SH) (SI) (SJ) (SK) (SL) (SM) (SN) (SO) (SP) (SQ) (SR) (SS) (ST) (SU) (SV) (SW) (SX) (SY) (SZ) (TA) (TB) (TC) (TD) (TE) (TF) (TG) (TH) (TI) (TJ) (TK) (TL) (TM) (TN) (TO) (TP) (TQ) (TR) (TS) (TT) (TU) (TV) (TW) (TX) (TY) (TZ) (UA) (UB) (UC) (UD) (UE) (UF) (UG) (UH) (UI) (UJ) (UK) (UL) (UM) (UN) (UO) (UP) (UQ) (UR) (US) (UT) (UU) (UV) (UW) (UX) (UY) (UZ) (VA) (VB) (VC) (VD) (VE) (VF) (VG) (VH) (VI) (VJ) (VK) (VL) (VM) (VN) (VO) (VP) (VQ) (VR) (VS) (VT) (VU) (VV) (VW) (VX) (VY) (VZ) (WA) (WB) (WC) (WD) (WE) (WF) (WG) (WH) (WI) (WJ) (WK) (WL) (WM) (WN) (WO) (WP) (WQ) (WR) (WS) (WT) (WU) (WV) (WW) (WX) (WY) (WZ) (XA) (XB) (XC) (XD) (XE) (XF) (XG) (XH) (XI) (XJ) (XK) (XL) (XM) (XN) (XO) (XP) (XQ) (XR) (XS) (XT) (XU) (XV) (XW) (XX) (XY) (XZ) (YA) (YB) (YC) (YD) (YE) (YF) (YG) (YH) (YI) (YJ) (YK) (YL) (YM) (YN) (YO) (YP) (YQ) (YR) (YS) (YT) (YU) (YV) (YW) (YX) (YY) (YZ) (ZA) (ZB) (ZC) (ZD) (ZE) (ZF) (ZG) (ZH) (ZI) (ZJ) (ZK) (ZL) (ZM) (ZN) (ZO) (ZP) (ZQ) (ZR) (ZS) (ZT) (ZU) (ZV) (ZW) (ZX) (ZY) (ZZ)

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 1200 UTC 17 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original Scale 1:20m

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F.28

MET-OFFICE PRINTED BY ** TOTAL PAGE.001 **

TOTAL ACCUMULATION
850MB MET BULB POT TEMP

DI 12Z TUESDAY 16/9/1997

RAINFALL IN MM DURING THE 6 HOURS ENDING AT VT

..:1 10 .5 R:10 B:11 C:12 D:13 E:14 F:15 G:16 H:17 J:18 K:19 L:20 M:21 N:22 P:23 Q:24 R:25-29 S:30-34 T:35-39 U:40-44 V:45-49 W:50-54 X:55-59 Y:60-64 Z:65 RND OVER

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

NON PROBABILITY AT MSL
 OTAL PPN RATE
 RESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z TUESDAY 16/9/1997 LMAIN

VT 02Z WEDNESDAY 17/9/1997

MM/HR AT VT

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

DT 00Z TUESDAY 16/9/1997 LMAIN

NON PROBABILITY AT MSL
OTAL PPN RATE
RESSURE AT MSL

T+12 VT 12Z TUESDAY 16/9/1997

NOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
OTAL PPN RATE
RESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z TUESDAY 16/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

.03 .1 .5 4.0 MM/HR AT VT

T+0 VT 0Z TUESDAY 16/9/1997

500-1000MB
500MB

--- THICKNESS DM.
--- HEIGHT DM.

T + 0

GMAIN

VT 00Z TUES 16/ 9/97

9/97

16/ 9/97

00Z TUES 16/ 9/97

MET_OFFICE-ARTIFAX_2 PAGE.001

16 SEP . 97 05:07

PHDA50 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

RUN TIME 03:32:24

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M

500-1000MB
THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE.001

PHDE50 EGRR 0000Z
CHART 27

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 05.40.11

16 SEP . 97 05:13

300MB

HEIGHT DM.

T + 0

GMAIN

TUES 16/ 9/97

VT 00Z

TUES 16/ 9/97

T 00Z

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-6 PAGE.001

16 SEP . 97 05:10

PHDA30 ECCR 0000Z

CHART 27

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:32.08

16 SEP . 97 05:16
MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-3 PAGE.001

300MB
HEIGHT DM.
T + 24
GMAIN
17/ 9/97
VT 00Z WED
16/ 9/97
00Z TUES

PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.39.53

99317

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 050

VALID 12 UTC 16 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 15 SEP 97

EGRR 1200Z

99316

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 100

VALID 12 UTC 16 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'

DATA TIME 12 UTC 15 SEP 97

EGRR 1200Z

99315

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 180

VALID 12 UTC 16 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'P'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 15 SEP 97

ECRR 1200Z

99314

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

CHART FOR FL 240
VALID 12 UTC 16 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY .PS.
DATA TIME 12 UTC 15 SEP 97

EORR 1200Z

99313

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE
CHART FOR FL 300

VALID 12 UTC 16 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'.
DATA TIME 12 UTC 15 SEP 97

EQRR 1200Z

STATION 08509
 LAGES (ACRES)
 TIME: 160000 +12 SEP 97
 MD Deg Kts
 MAX WINDS: NIL

150	230	23
200	310	28
251	300	35
301	310	38
357	295	35
425	280	32
508	285	33
604	285	29
705	285	28
877	295	31
938	285	32
983	280	29
1005	275	24

Parts: A C D missing

STATION: 08509
 LAJES (ACRES)
 TIME: 160000 +36 SEP 97

mb	Dir	Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL		
150	240	16
201	240	33
251	230	42
302	225	45
358	240	38
426	255	23
510	265	15
607	280	15
709	285	10
804	275	9
882	290	11
944	295	12
989	295	12
1011	290	10

Parts : A C D Missing

A576

From 0Z 10/ 9/1997 to 18Z 16/ 9/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 19-May-1998 08:46

A576 16-SEP-97

P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles)(125031-132835) + P2 FL200-50'(133010-135233)

A576 16-SEP-97

P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles)(135233-142804) + P4 FL200-50' (+bottles)(142925-145759)

A576 16-SEP-97

P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles)(145759-153124) + P6 FL200-50' (+bottles)(153518-160821)

A576 16-SEP-97

P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2)(160821-170217) + P8 FL200-FL50(170217-171814)

A576 16-SEP-97

P9 FL50-FL150(171814-172827) + P10 FL50-FL50(173141-174211)

A576 16-SEP-97

P11 FL50-FL150(174211-175252) + P12 FL150-FL50(175252-180440)

A576 16-SEP-97

P13 FL50-FL150(180727-181807) + P14 FL150-FL50(181807-182818)

A576 16-SEP-97

P15 FL50-FL150 (183040-184102)

A576 16-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 122826-124329 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:26

A576 16-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 122826-124329 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:26

A576 16-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 122826-124329 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:26

A576 16-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 122826-124329 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:26

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 753.528
 Standard dev 0.381991
 Max value 754.306
 Min value 752.366

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 284.699
 Standard dev 0.362565
 Max value 285.549
 Min value 284.075

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 276.847
 Standard dev 2.97148
 Max value 281.645
 Min value 273.355

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 40.0336
 Standard dev 8.77087
 Max value 54.9080
 Min value 24.5334

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
 No of obs 904
 Mean 1.720670e-06
 Standard dev 2.084710e-06
 Max value 7.850838e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 2428.78
 Standard dev 4.04254
 Max value 2441.08
 Min value 2420.56

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 36.0385
 Standard dev 0.267009
 Max value 36.4960
 Min value 35.5875

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 904
 Mean -25.9694
 Standard dev 0.252330
 Max value -25.5698
 Min value -26.4298

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 904
 Mean -1.30124
 Standard dev 0.601960
 Max value -2.217865e-02
 Min value -2.52193

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 13.8508
 Standard dev 0.971444
 Max value 15.8555
 Min value 11.7618

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 904
 Mean -0.346951
 Standard dev 0.331501
 Max value 0.270744
 Min value -1.41764

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 13.9278
 Standard dev 0.928137
 Max value 15.8840
 Min value 11.8987

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 275.367

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 904
 Mean 149.047
 Standard dev 7.88512
 Max value 153.239
 Min value 113.227

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 217.570

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:35

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:36

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 22-May-1998 15:34

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:36

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:36

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:36

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:36

A576 16-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 125031-132835 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:36

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 2285
Mean 711.477
Standard dev 170.322
Max value 1013.23
Min value 467.489

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 2285
Mean 279.947
Standard dev 10.3697
Max value 296.335
Min value 263.464

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 2285
Mean 270.132
Standard dev 17.5300
Max value 294.305
Min value 240.573

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 2285
Mean 43.6666
Standard dev 13.1646
Max value 64.8044
Min value 23.9724

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
No of obs 2285
Mean 4.889831e-07
Standard dev 9.320399e-07
Max value 4.602625e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 2285
Mean 3067.85
Standard dev 1892.63
Max value 6066.94
Min value 0.183724

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2285
Mean 34.5118
Standard dev 0.536000
Max value 35.2357
Min value 33.4093

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2285
Mean -27.3714
Standard dev 0.230086
Max value -26.7973
Min value -27.5626

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2285
Mean -2.57797
Standard dev 1.26313
Max value -9.354401e-02
Min value -7.57174

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2285
Mean 9.88707
Standard dev 1.17438
Max value 12.6608
Min value 6.14990

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2285
Mean -0.912343
Standard dev 0.562684
Max value 1.83977
Min value -2.22289

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 2285
Mean 10.3078
Standard dev 1.06686
Max value 12.9928
Min value 6.24936

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 284.613

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 2285
Mean 109.574
Standard dev 9.89126
Max value 125.834
Min value 93.4743

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 197.538

A576 16-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' From 133010-135233 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:41

A576 16-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' From 133010-135233 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:42

A576 16-SEP-97 P2 FL200-50' From 133010-135233 Plotted 22-May-1998 15:19

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 22-May-1998 15:48

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

A576 16-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 135233-142804 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:49

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2130
Mean 709.258
Standard dev 161.380
Max value 1016.02
Min value 467.351

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2130
Mean 279.768
Standard dev 10.5613
Max value 298.626
Min value 260.889

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2130
Mean 267.171
Standard dev 19.4404
Max value 296.057
Min value 232.894

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2130
Mean 46.6050
Standard dev 15.1447
Max value 74.6110
Min value 15.5810

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2130
Mean 5.555021e-08
Standard dev 2.647300e-07
Max value 1.684117e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2130
Mean 3075.08
Standard dev 1801.51
Max value 6069.09
Min value -23.0385

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2130
Mean 31.0488
Standard dev 0.557089
Max value 31.9542
Min value 30.0104

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2130
Mean -27.7201
Standard dev 0.182945
Max value -27.3795
Min value -28.0306

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2130
Mean 1.32579
Standard dev 3.60431
Max value 10.5952
Min value -3.39765

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2130
Mean 11.6753
Standard dev 4.17686
Max value 18.7348
Min value 2.30379

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2130
Mean -0.907850
Standard dev 0.522045
Max value 1.32642
Min value -2.30174

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2129
Mean 12.1762
Standard dev 4.50306
Max value 20.0659
Min value 2.82821

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 263.522

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2130
Mean 110.594
Standard dev 9.16113
Max value 127.040
Min value 91.6126

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 196.072

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 22-May-1998 15:52

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

A576 16-SEP-97 P4 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 142925-145759 Plotted 6-May-1998 18:53

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1712
Mean 747.226
Standard dev 157.104
Max value 1018.61
Min value 467.092

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1712
Mean 282.181
Standard dev 10.3438
Max value 298.984
Min value 260.450

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1712
Mean 275.201
Standard dev 13.1336
Max value 294.651
Min value 240.364

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1712
Mean 34.6235
Standard dev 19.3446
Max value 74.7802
Min value 12.4668

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 1712
Mean 2.792734e-08
Standard dev 1.151844e-07
Max value 8.049012e-07
Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1712
Mean 2643.22
Standard dev 1713.95
Max value 6073.13
Min value -44.5244

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1712
Mean 29.0335
Standard dev 0.475699
Max value 29.9135
Min value 28.2525

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1712
Mean -28.1195
Standard dev 5.586427e-02
Max value -28.0416
Min value -28.2437

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1712
Mean -7.331852e-02
Standard dev 1.62798
Max value 2.97029
Min value -3.34102

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1712
Mean 7.90770
Standard dev 1.77702
Max value 11.6613
Min value 2.76270

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1712
Mean 0.197222
Standard dev 0.483588
Max value 1.46394
Min value -1.16811

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1711
Mean 8.08484
Standard dev 1.72813
Max value 11.7369
Min value 2.76594

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 270.531

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1712
Mean 109.152
Standard dev 10.0546
Max value 132.968
Min value 91.8322

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 186.103

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 22-May-1998 15:59

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

A576 16-SEP-97 P5 50'-FL200 (+bottles) From 145759-153124 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:00

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2006
Mean 734.660
Standard dev 186.402
Max value 1018.61
Min value 462.736

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2006
Mean 281.466
Standard dev 11.9093
Max value 298.943
Min value 261.242

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2006
Mean 267.847
Standard dev 18.7014
Max value 294.386
Min value 239.031

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2006
Mean 42.5574
Standard dev 26.0383
Max value 84.7997
Min value 14.3034

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2006
Mean 2.775312e-07
Standard dev 7.388245e-07
Max value 5.017811e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2006
Mean 2843.69
Standard dev 2052.73
Max value 6141.27
Min value -44.5244

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2006
Mean 27.3582
Standard dev 0.551142
Max value 28.2525
Min value 26.3484

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2006
Mean -28.4864
Standard dev 0.152440
Max value -28.2437
Min value -28.7422

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2006
Mean -0.648230
Standard dev 1.84215
Max value 3.13998
Min value -4.44277

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2006
Mean 5.88958
Standard dev 1.92692
Max value 9.40937
Min value 2.16673

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2006
Mean -0.877725
Standard dev 0.482005
Max value 0.928543
Min value -1.61996

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2006
Mean 6.26135
Standard dev 1.73415
Max value 9.41614
Min value 2.53620

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 276.281

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2006
Mean 108.939
Standard dev 10.2087
Max value 128.877
Min value 92.4366

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 193.141

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bolies) From 153518-160821 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:07

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 153518-160821 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:07

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 153518-160821 Plotted 22-May-1998 16:07

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 153518-160821 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:07

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 153518-160821 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:07

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 153518-160821 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:07

A576 16-SEP-97 P6 FL200-50' (+bottles) From 153518-160821 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:07

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1984
Mean 755.437
Standard dev 168.897
Max value 1017.72
Min value 464.293

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1984
Mean 283.346
Standard dev 10.8794
Max value 299.096
Min value 261.648

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1984
Mean 269.464
Standard dev 18.0236
Max value 294.819
Min value 235.544

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1984
Mean 38.3458
Standard dev 24.9599
Max value 86.9256
Min value 9.64946

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 1984
Mean 6.369831e-07
Standard dev 8.602622e-07
Max value 3.320436e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1984
Mean 2576.97
Standard dev 1834.13
Max value 6116.85
Min value -37.1167

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1984
Mean 25.0240
Standard dev 1.39694
Max value 26.0776
Min value -32.0909

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1984
Mean -29.0180
Standard dev 0.950039
Max value 12.7849
Min value -29.3030

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1984
Mean -4.01498
Standard dev 135.629
Max value 4.71049
Min value -6041.15

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1984
Mean 0.278776
Standard dev 3.11135
Max value 31.7301
Min value -5.18401

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1984
Mean -2.48285
Standard dev 119.275
Max value 1.59050
Min value -5312.55

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1982
Mean 3.74627
Standard dev 1.53362
Max value 7.44257
Min value 0.115997

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 356.028

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1984
Mean 109.588
Standard dev 11.0613
Max value 133.826
Min value 91.4071

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 193.013

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 22-May-1998 16:20

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 *Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17*

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17

A576 16-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL200 (+bottles+R2) From 160821-170217 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:17

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 3237
Mean 769.760
Standard dev 199.842
Max value 1017.60
Min value 463.547

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 3237
Mean 283.532
Standard dev 12.9122
Max value 299.103
Min value 260.231

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 3237
Mean 271.993
Standard dev 19.4295
Max value 294.996
Min value 240.613

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 3237
Mean 39.6606
Standard dev 24.3795
Max value 82.9760
Min value 13.4154

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 3237
Mean 1.262941e-06
Standard dev 1.364015e-06
Max value 6.751819e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

No good data

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 3237
Mean 2492.43
Standard dev 2173.04
Max value 6128.54
Min value -36.1742

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3237
Mean 25.3231
Standard dev 0.880877
Max value 26.9854
Min value 24.0160

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3237
Mean -28.9904
Standard dev 0.231083
Max value -28.5722
Min value -29.3435

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3237
Mean -3.661041e-02
Standard dev 2.36502
Max value 6.03359
Min value -4.35841

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3237
Mean -2.06231
Standard dev 3.79752
Max value 8.29032
Min value -7.08311

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3237
Mean -0.571018
Standard dev 0.500673
Max value 1.18452
Min value -2.03392

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 3237
Mean 4.61823
Standard dev 1.71335
Max value 8.65067
Min value 0.514800

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 88.9830

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 3237
Mean 110.128
Standard dev 13.8526
Max value 140.150
Min value 90.0476

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 13.1769

A576 16-SEP-97 P8 FL200-FL50 From 170217-171814 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:21

A576 16-SEP-97 P8 FL200-FL50 From 170217-171814 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:21

A576 16-SEP-97 P8 FL200-FL50 From 170217-171814 Plotted 22-May-1998 16:24

A576 16-SEP-97 P9 FL50-FL150 From 171814-172827 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:23

A576 16-SEP-97 P9 FL50-FL150 From 171814-172827 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:23

A576 16-SEP-97 P9 FL50-FL150 From 171814-172827 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:21

A576 16-SEP-97 P10 F150-FL50 From 173141-174211 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:25

A576 16-SEP-97 P10 F150-FL50 From 173141-174211 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:25

A576 16-SEP-97 P10 F150-FL50 From 173141-174211 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:24

A576 16-SEP-97 P11 FL50-FL150 From 174211-175252 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:28

A576 16-SEP-97 P11 FL50-FL150 From 174211-175252 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:28

A576 16-SEP-97 P11 FL50-FL150 From 174211-175252 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:27

A576 16-SEP-97 P12 FL150-FL50 From 175252-180440 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:30

A576 16-SEP-97 P12 FL150-FL50 From 175252-180440 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:30

A576 16-SEP-97 P12 FL150-FL50 From 175252-180440 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:31

A576 16-SEP-97 P13 FL50-FL150 From 180727-181807 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:33

A576 16-SEP-97

P13 FL50-FL150 From 180727-181807 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:33

A576 16-SEP-97 P13 FL50-FL150 From 180727-181807 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:34

A576 16-SEP-97 P14 FL150-FL50 From 181807-182818 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:35

A576 16-SEP-97 P14 FL150-FL50 From 181807-182818 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:35

A576 16-SEP-97 P14 FL150-FL50 From 181807-182818 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:37

A576 16-SEP-97 P15 FL50-FL150 From 183040-184102 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:37

A576 16-SEP-97 P15 FL50-FL150 From 183040-184102 Plotted 6-May-1998 19:37

A576 16-SEP-97 P15 FL50-FL150 From 183040-184102 Plotted 27-May-1998 09:41

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Particle Data

- **CNC:** Condensation nucleus counter (this data is provisional and requires further validation). The measurement is from a commercial instrument: TSI INC Model 3025A. Although CNC data were recorded on the flight no post flight processing has been carried out. Rather than delay this booklet further, I have decided to wait and process the data when the validation has been carried out by the cloud physics group.
- **PSAP:** The Radiance Research Particle Soot Absorption Photometer gives a measurement of optical absorption by black carbon, using a quartz filter with the absorption measured at 565 nm.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (data not quality controlled). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using approximate scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_y) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Only one NO_y channel was available for this flight. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU:
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

ARASF

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